

Standard Operating Procedure

SOP/ENL/01/1.0

Semi-static Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity Test

Version: 1.0

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I. Purpose

The purpose of this SOP is to document the procedures of the semi-static zebrafish embryo toxicity test.

II. Objective of the test

The objective of this test is to evaluate the toxicity of nanomaterials in the embryos of zebrafish in a semi-static exposure.

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III. Validity of the test

For the test results to be valid, the following criteria apply:

- Mortality in the negative control is not higher than 10% at the end of the test.
- Mortality in the positive control is higher than 30% at the end of the test.
- Hatching in the negative control is higher than 80% at the end of the test.

IV. Description of the method

a. Equipment and material

The following equipment and material are needed to perform the test:

- Glass tanks
- Marbles
- Heater
- Plastic tubing and aeration stones
- Fish net
- Inverted microscope
- Equipment to take photographs of eggs/embryos
- Equipment to control time
- Plastic petri dish
- 24-well plates
- Pipettes
- Containers for the preparation of test concentrations
- Equipment for determination of water parameters such as: pH, temperature, conductivity, hardness and dissolved oxygen.

b. Test organisms

Test organisms should be zebrafish's embryos (*Danio rerio*).

c. Test chambers

Test chambers should be 24-well plates.

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d. Water and test conditions

Test water should be filtered reconstituted freshwater with a conductivity at least 300 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Plates should be maintained at 27°C ($\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) and photoperiod of 14:10 (L:D).

e. Duration of test

The test has a duration of 80 hours post fertilization (hpf).

V. Egg production

Female and male adult fish (5F:5M) are transfer into breeding cages on the day before the test. At least two cages should be set to assure a sufficient number of eggs. Measures should be taken to prevent predation of the eggs by the adult fish (e.g. placing marbles at the bottom of the tanks; additional cage with a net bottom).

One hour after the onset of light the eggs are carefully collected from the breeding cages and cleaned with filtered reconstituted freshwater.

VI. Procedure

a. Controls

A negative control of freshwater and a positive control of 4 mg/L 3, 4-dichloroaniline are used.

If a solvent/stabilizer is used to disperse the nanomaterials a solvent /stabilizer control is added.

b. Test concentrations

At least five test concentrations should be used separated by a dilution factor of 10. The nanomaterial stock solution should be dispersed as required and the test concentrations prepared in filtered reconstituted freshwater whenever possible.

c. Conditions of exposure

The embryos should be exposed to the test concentrations as soon as possible.

Ten embryos are distributed in each well according to the layout showed in figure 1. Each well should be filled with 2 mL of the respective concentration.

Figure 1. Layout of the 24-well plate. nC – negative control; pC – positive control; 1-5 – nanomaterials concentrations; sC = solvent control; L1 – L4 – line number of the plate.

d. Exposure concentrations renewal

Exposure medium should be renewed after 24, 48 and 72 hours. In every renewal, the number of dead embryos should be verified and removed from the wells.

e. Evaluations

Several parameters should be evaluated during the test taking into consideration the development of the embryos described by Kimmel *et al.* (1995). Photographs should be taken in some of the time points for posterior analysis. The defined time points and evaluated parameters are as follow (table 1):

Table 1. Time points and evaluations during the test.

Time point	Observations
8 hpf	Mortality
	Take photos of L1 and L3 (every embryo)
32 hpf	Mortality
	Hatching
	Heart beat for 10 seconds (5 eggs/well in L2 and L4)

Time point	Observations
32hpf	Spontaneous movement (L2 and L4)
	Lack of somite formation (whole plate)
	Non-detachment of the tail (whole plate)
	Take photos of L2 and L4 (5 eggs/well)
56 hpf	Mortality (whole plate)
	Hatching (whole plate)
	Heart beat 10 seconds (5 eggs/well in L1 and L3)
	Lack of somite formation (whole plate)
	Non-detachment of the tail (whole plate)
80 hpf	Take photos of L1 and L3 (5 eggs/well)
	Mortality (whole plate)
	Hatching (whole plate)
	Free swimming (whole plate)
	Lack of somite formation (whole plate)
	Non-detachment of the tail (whole plate)

Always register and take photos of all malformations. Photos from different evaluation stages can be found in figure 2.

Figure 2. Zebrafish evaluation stages; A – embryo at 8hpf, B - dead embryo at 8hpf, C – larvae at 32hpf, D – larvae at 56 hpf.

f. Water Quality Measurements

The following parameters should be measure for each concentration at the beginning and at the end of the test: temperature, pH, conductivity, alkalinity and dissolved oxygen. Whenever possible the parameters should be access in each test well.

The parameters should be maintained within the following ranges (table 2):

Table 2. Acceptable ranges for the water parameters

Parameters	Range
Temperature	27°C ± 1°C
pH	6.5 - 8.5
Dissolved oxygen	≥ 80 %

g. Nanomaterials' quantification

The real concentration of nanomaterials in each well should be assessed at all concentrations (unless below the limit of detection- LoQ for the analytical method). This quantification should be performed at the beginning and end of the test and also in the medium collected from the daily renewal.

h. Photograph analysis

The data that should be obtained from the photographs taken in each time point can be found in table 3, as well as details of measurements in figure 3.

Table 3. Parameters obtained from the photographs.

Time point	Observations
8 hpf (fig. 3)	Yolk and egg diameter (equatorial and polar)
	Epibolic arc perimeter
32 hpf (fig. 4)	Eye and pupil diameter (equatorial and polar)
	Yolk and egg diameter (equatorial and polar)
	Head-trunk angle
56 hpf (fig. 5)	Eye and yolk diameter (equatorial and polar)
	Larvae length
	Yolk extension

Figure 3. Measurements to be obtain from embryos at 8hpf. A1 – yolk diameter (e – equatorial; p – polar) and epibolic arc perimeter (black long dash); A2 – egg diameter (e – equatorial; p – polar). red dot line – polar measurement; red solid line – equatorial measurement.

Figure 4. Measurements obtain from embryos at 32hpf. B1 – yolk diameter (e – equatorial; p – polar) and head-trunk angle (black line); B2 – egg diameter (e – equatorial; p – polar); B3 – pupil diameter (e – equatorial; p – polar) ; B4 – eye diameter (e – equatorial; p – polar); red dot line – polar measurement; red solid line – equatorial measurement.

Figure 5. Measurements obtain from a larvae at 56hpf. C1 – yolk diameter (*e* – equatorial; *p* – polar) and eye diameter (*e* – equatorial; *p* – polar); C2 – larvae and yolk length

VII. Data and statistical analysis

Calculate the percentage of the following parameters for each concentration: epiboly at 8hpf, spontaneous movement at 32hpf, hatching at 56hpf, survival and free-swimming at 80hpf.

Calculate the values of the following parameters for each concentration: yolk volume and egg volume at 8 and 32hpf, pupil surface, eye surface and head-trunk angle index at 32hpf, cardiac frequency at 32 and 56hpf and larvae length and yolk volume and extension at 56hpf.

Appropriated statistical methods should be applied to detect differences between the control and the concentrations of exposure for the parameters evaluated. Moreover, an analysis of covariance should be applied whenever possible for: yolk volume vs egg volume, pupil surface vs eye surface and larvae length vs yolk extension.

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VIII. References

Kimmel CB, Ballard WW, Kimmel SR, Ullmann B, Schilling TF. Stages of embryonic development of the zebrafish. *Dev Dyn.* 1995 Jul;203(3):253-310. doi: 10.1002/aja.1002030302.